

THE NEED FOR A SOCIO-GEOGRAPHICAL APPROACH TO THE STUDY OF ETHNOECOLOGICAL CULTURE

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ABSTRACT

Since the purpose of this study is to study the geographical aspects of ethno-ecological culture, a systematic approach is necessary here, which provides the opportunity to study natural and social directions at the same time. The reason is that social, economic, natural and ecological indicators and their interrelationship are taken as elements of ethno-ecological culture.

Keywords: ethno-ecological culture, natural-ecological character, historical approach, economic-cultural types, historical ethnographic regions.

INTRODUCTION

A complex approach is of particular importance in conducting ethnoecological research, because these studies have a natural and social nature at the same time. Although most of the problems waiting to be solved in the research are of a natural-ecological nature, the solution of socio-historical issues plays a major role in their solution. Therefore, in the research work, special attention is paid to the historical and ecological approaches that incorporate complex views [1, 2, 7, 8].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Today, the main indicators of the geoeological scientific direction are considered to be the main indicators of the scientific direction of geoeology, the amount of use and production of nature, the number of people, the amount of natural resources. there is a need to monitor changes in indicators such as the scale of use, the amount of anthropogenic pressure on nature, ecological and ethno-ecological landscape balance

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in space and time [3, 4]. This, in turn, shows the need for a historical approach along with an innovative approach to maintaining ecological balance.

The principles, types and form of territorial organization of the community in economic and social geography may change under the influence of various factors. V. A. Pulyarkin, on the example of countries of the world, justified the fact that this situation can be more clearly manifested in the process of using nature, including land resources [5, 6]. Analyzing based on these methodological bases, Y.I.Akhmadaliyev proposed to distinguish three types of regional organization of the use of natural resources in regional conditions. Based on the purpose of using nature, these types are conventionally called natural-organizational, commodity-targeted and program-targeted [2].

RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

We called the first type of use of nature based on the use of the natural resources of the region, which existed in the Fergana Valley until the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, because the organizational aspects of the issue were not so developed during this period. In this type of territorial organization of the use of nature, relief, climate, soil characteristics, the closed position of the valley, as well as the national-ethnic characteristics, skills, skills and habits of the population are taken into account. This type is usually formed over a long historical period, and the skills, competences and experiences accumulated in it are based on a harmonious, balanced relationship with nature. Therefore, from an ecological point of view, this species is the most robust and is worth studying for this purpose.

If the interactions of the "Ethno-landscape-economy" system are placed in the form of "geotriions", it will be shown that the main burden falls on the economy, and that it is carried out in accordance with the landscape indicators in the territorial organization of the economy. It is shown that only the indicators of management that correspond to the landscape requirements of the ethnos are preserved as "skills-qualifications-traditions". With the development of "ethno-landscape-economy"

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relations, the amount of natural landscapes (biosphere) in any region decreases and its place is taken by economic indicators (technosphere).

As relations in the "ethno-landscape-economy" system improve, [6, 9] the first type is replaced by the commodity type of territorial organization of the use of nature. In this type, along with the natural possibilities of the region, subjective factors (for example, the increase in demand for commodity crops, the penetration of foreign ethnic groups into the landscape) are also taken into account. As a result, the natural landscape features of the region are changed more, the achievements of scientific and technical development are widely used. Although the economic efficiency is high, the ground is prepared for the emergence of geo-ecological problems. This species existed in the Fergana Valley from 1876 to 1991.

Interactions of the "ethno-landscape-economy" system can be observed from the form of "geotriions" that the main burden falls on the landscape. Forced adaptation of the landscape to economic indicators, over-intensification of land reclamation and irrigation works, and changes in the regime and direction of rivers are observed. In our conditions, irrigation works are carried out with the help of a machine (pump), and areas where it is absolutely forbidden to release water (for example, hills) are irrigated. writes that it causes [7, 8]. In this type, the most important aspect for this study is the interaction between the local ethnic groups and the "advanced" ethnic groups that entered (or invaded) their territory. According to L. N. Gumelev, "advanced, foreign or alien" ethnic groups teach the highly technical methods of using nature in their landscapes to the local ethnic groups and start using them in their landscapes [9].

CONCLUSION

The third, i.e., "program-objective type" of "ethno-landscape-economy" system relations, is typical for advanced independent countries, which conduct economy based on the principles of sustainable development of nature use. In the Fergana Valley, the transition to this type began after our independence. In the "geotriions" reflecting the interaction of "ethno-landscape-economy", it can be seen that each component has an

equal amount of weight. However, even in this type, the biosphere is increasingly being replaced by the technosphere and ethnosphere, as can be seen from the diagram.

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